

Kinetic Investigation of The Chromium (III) Alanine Complex In The Presence of Hexacyanoferrate (III) Ion and Catalyst Os(VIII)

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For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>**Tejal Singh**Assistant Professor
Department Of Chemistry
S. P. M. College
Udantpuri, Bihar, India**Abstract**

Amino acids and the metal complexes they contain are key components of every biological system's metabolism. Amino acids and metal complexes can undergo a wide range of reactions in both acidic and alkaline conditions. This study investigated the reactivity of the Chromium (III) alanine complex (CrA) in an alkaline solution. The kinetics of oxidation of Chromium (III) alanine complex by alkaline Os(VIII) and the hexacyanoferrate (III) ion, were examined in the temperature range of 303 K to 323 K and substrate range of 0.01M to 0.1M. The reaction rate with respect to $[Fe(CN_6)]^{3-}$ was found to be zero, whereas that for Os (VIII) was one.

Keywords

Kinetics, Oxidation, Chromium (III) Alanine, Osmium (VIII), Hexacyanoferrate (III), Complex.

Introduction

Alanine is a non-essential amino acid found in high concentrations in the plasma. It is highly concentrated in muscle and one among the most significant amino acids generated by muscle, serving as a primary energy source^{2,21}. Transamination converts pyruvate into it. L-Alanine is a metabolite generated by *Escherichia coli*^{2,21}. Understanding the physicochemical properties and medicinal applications of alanine is critical in biochemistry, pharmacology, and clinical diagnostics⁴. More recent study has demonstrated that alanine has a role in immune responses and might be used as a biomarker.¹³

Transition metal-amino acid complexes have been extensively researched for their antimicrobial properties. They have been tested against a variety of bacteria, yielding encouraging results^{6,1}. Transition metal-amino acid complexes have been extensively explored for antimicrobial characteristics. They have been tested against a variety of bacteria and show promising results^{12,19,20}. The harmless Cr (III) is necessary for human, animal, and plant health¹. Chromium was recently acknowledged as a vital element³. Chromium is biologically significant in both its trivalent and hexavalent forms, while the trivalent state is more frequent. It occurs in the earth's crust as chromates, dichromates, and so on. Chromium is used in tanning, wood preservation, pigments, and plastic colors⁷. Metal complexes of amino acids have been oxidized, yielding various compounds^{9,18}.

Objective of study

This paper's primary goal is to provide a concise overview and investigation of the existing literature on the oxidation of amino acid metal complexes by hexacyanoferrate (III) reagents and catalyst Os (VIII). It also encourages the various contributions made to the relevant and fascinating field of amino acid and their metal complexes.

Review of Literature

Short communication kinetics of chromium (III)-oxidation in topsoils was studied by Bohm et al., (2004). Physicochemical properties and medical significance of alanine was studied by Gaybullayevna (2025). Compound of chromium (III) with alanine was studied by Green and Ang (1955). Synthesis and antibacterial activity of M(II) schiff-base complex were studied by Johari (2009). Toxicity of heavy metals; Effects of Cr and Se on Human health was studied by Kennis (1992). Kinetics of oxidation of amino acids by alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III), was studied by Mahanti and Laloo (1990). Kinetics and mechanism of the osmium (VIII)-catalyzed oxidation of phosphite by hexacyanoferrate (III) ion in aqueous alkaline media was studied by Mohan and Gupta (1977). Synthesis, Characterization, and Biological Evaluation of Chromium (III) Complexes of Alanine and Valine was studied by Musa et al. (2019). D-Alanine and immune modulation in infection was studied by Nakamura (2018). Osmium (VIII) Catalyzed Oxidation of Diclofenac Sodium by Diperiodatoargentate (III) Complex in Aqueous Alkaline Medium was studied by Patil et al. (2009). Reaction kinetics of sonochemical oxidation of potassium hexacyanoferrate (II) in aqueous solutions was studied by Rajchel-Mieldzioc et al. (2020), Mahantesh A., Angadi and Tuwar S. M., Kinetics and mechanism of Ruthenium (III) catalyzed oxidation of l-proline by hexacyanoferrate (III) in aqueous alkali was studied by Sharanabasamma (2011). Antibacterial activity of copper and cobalt amino acids complexes was studied by Stanila et al. (2011). Complexes of chromium (III) with DL- α -alanine, Theory and structure of complex compounds was studied by Starosta and Pajdowski (1964). Ph. D. Thesis of Singh, Melkani and Mehta of Kumaun University and text books for analysis was also studied.

Methodology

All of these compounds, including Alanine, osmium tetroxide, sodium hydroxide, ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol, potassium hydrogen phthalates, oxalic acid, potassium hydroxide,

chromium nitrate, and phenolphthalein, have been produced by E. Merck India Ltd. Fluka Puriss synthesized potassium hexacyanoferrate (III). All of the solutions were made in Pyrex glass receptacles with triple-distilled conductivity water.

Preparation of Chromium (III) alanine complex [CrA]

To make the complex, combine 20 mL of chromium nitrate solution with 25 mL of amino acid alanine solution and stir at 60°C for 2 hours. A purple precipitate was produced, washed with ethanol, recrystallized in methanol, and stored in a desiccator^{5,6,10,12,19,20}.

Standardisation of Osmium tetroxide

One gram of OsO₄ glass tube was taken. It was shattered into a beaker with 0.5 N sodium hydroxide solution. The glass tube fragments were removed from the solution. These pieces were repeatedly washed in the same beaker with distilled water until the solid was totally dissolved. Following that, the solution was transferred to a 1-litre measuring flask. Iodometric standardization of the OsO₄ solution was also performed^{9,11}.

λ_{\max} of potassium hexacyanoferrate (III)

The absorbance of unreacted (0.001M) potassium hexacyanoferrate (III), which would be used as the oxidant, was measured at various wavelengths using a double beam Biosync Teknology Spectrophotometer, model number BST 2800, and an Elico-Digital Spectrophotometer, model CL-27. A graph of absorbance vs. wavelength reveals λ_{\max} (420 nm)^{9,18} for potassium hexacyanoferrate (III).

Molar absorption coefficient of potassium hexacyanoferrate (III)

The molar absorbance coefficient for potassium hexacyanoferrate (III) was found at 420 nm to be 990 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹, which is consistent with the quoted value (990 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)^{16,18}.

Measurement of the rate constants

Standard techniques were utilized to create the reaction mixtures. The reaction containers were filled with a combination of the predicted substrate and NaOH content. The usual NaCl solutions preserved their ionic strength. With a 5 mL pipette, the reaction mixture was swiftly extracted and transferred to the spectrophotometer's sample tube. The absorbance of the reaction mixture at 420 nm was measured using a double beam Biosync Teknology Spectrophotometer (BST 2800) and an Elico-Digital Spectrophotometer (CL-27)^{9,18}.

In the absence of a catalyst, the reactions were discovered to be too slow to examine in alkaline media. Without a catalyst in alkaline media, the oxidation of Chromium (III) alanine complex took about one to two days to complete. Hence To accelerate the reactions, an Os (VIII) catalyst was added to the reaction mixtures. It was revealed that in the presence of an Os (VIII) catalyst, alkaline reactions were practically complete. For more than two half-lives, the absorbance vs time graphs were almost linear, indicating a zero-order interaction with potassium hexacyanoferrate (III). In each example, the slope of the linear plot of absorbance vs time was calculated. The rate constant k_0 was calculated using the following formula¹⁸:

$$\text{Rate Constant } (k_0) = \frac{\text{Slope}}{990} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1: Zero order plot for the of oxidation of Chromium (III) alanine complex

The kinetic research using Os (VIII) as a catalyst followed the same procedure.

Stoichiometry of the reactions

The reactions' stoichiometry was determined under the following two conditions.

1. [Substrate] >> [K₃[Fe(CN)₆]
2. [Substrate] << [K₃[Fe(CN)₆]

The experimental condition (i) offers information on the substrate's initial oxidation product, whereas condition (ii) provides information on the whole oxidation process. Before beginning the process, the [hexacyanoferrate (III)] was determined, and the absorbance at 420 nm was calculated until it reached a constant value. The quantity of unreacted [hexacyanoferrate (III)] was determined using equation (1).

For the Chromium (III) alanine complex, the stoichiometry ratio between [hexacyanoferrate (III)] and [substrate] is 6:1.

Thus, the stoichiometric equations for the oxidation Chromium (III) alanine complex is as follows:

Product Analysis

The product was tested in two different experimental settings.

1. [substrate] >> [hexacyanoferrate]
2. [substrate] << [hexacyanoferrate]
3. When substrate << [hexacyanoferrate]

This experimental condition yields the substrates' final oxidation products.

The principal oxidation products of the Chromium (III) alanine complex were identified as CrO₃, NH₃, CH₃CHO, and CO₂. CrO₃ is a highly reactive species that converts to Cr₂O₃ after some time.

The predominant oxidation product was found as Cr₂O₃, which was validated by the oxidative melt/colored test¹⁴. Aldehyde was verified with 2, 4-DNP, ammonia was confirmed using Nessler's reagent¹⁵, and CO₂ was qualitatively identified by passing the freed gas through lime water.

Result and Discussion**Order with Respect to Hexacyanoferrate (III)**

At 303K, the reaction order for hexacyanoferrate (III) was determined using constant [substrate], [Os (VIII)], [OH⁻], and ionic strength. The [hexacyanoferrate (III)] was adjusted from 8.0x10⁻⁴ to 16x10⁻⁴. Because Beer's rule does not apply at higher concentrations, the larger amounts in the first [hexacyanoferrate (III)] were irrelevant. Fig. 1 depicts the absorbance vs time plots for the oxidation of Chromium (III) alanine in this study, indicating that order was zero in the presence of hexacyanoferrate (III). The fact that the k_o values remained constant with changes in the beginning [hexacyanoferrate (III)] but the t_{1/2} values increased with the increase in [hexacyanoferrate (III)] provided more support for the zero-order process in relation to [hexacyanoferrate (III)].

Table 1: The values of k_o and $t_{1/2}$ at different initial [hexacyanoferrate (III)] in the oxidation of Chromium (III) alanine.

Temp.= 303K, 10^2 [CrA] = 2.0 mol dm⁻³, 10^2 [OH⁻] = 5.0 mol dm⁻³,
 10^3 Os (VIII) = 2.50 mol dm⁻³ and μ = 1.0 mol dm⁻³

10^4 [Fe(CN) ₆ ³⁻] (mol dm ⁻³)	8.0	10.0	12.0	14.0	16.0
$10^6 k_o$ (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	28.1838	27.2957	27.8121	27.6717	27.9596
Half life period $t_{1/2}$ (minutes)	21.48	25.65	32.36	39.54	48.47

Dependence on [OH⁻]

Chromium (III) alanine showed linear graphs between k_o and [OH⁻]. Fig. 2 provides illustrations of these plots. Chromium (III) alanine's ten-fold variation in [OH⁻] was examined at five different temperatures since increased [OH⁻] was associated with a departure from zero order behaviour. Table 2 presents a compilation of the results.

Table 2: Effect of [OH⁻] on the hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation of Chromium (III) alanine

10^2 [CrA] = 2.0 mol dm⁻³, 10^3 [Fe(CN)₆³⁻] = 1.2 mol dm⁻³,
 10^3 Os [VIII] = 2.50 mol dm⁻³ and μ = 1.0 mol dm⁻³.

Temp. (K)	10^2 [OH ⁻] (mol dm ⁻³)				
	1	3	5	7.5	10
	$10^5 k_o$ (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)				
303	3.456	3.989	5.223	7.636	8.987
308	5.374	7.223	7.965	10.817	11.985
313	6.976	8.662	10.031	13.045	15.98
318	8.956	11.553	14.51	16.885	18.82
323	12.897	17.876	21.098	24.546	30.324

Fig. 2: k_o vs [OH⁻] plots for the oxidation of [CrA] at 303K, 308K, 313K, 318K and 323K

Dependence on [Os (VIII)]:

The alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation of chromium (III) alanine was investigated at different [Os (VIII)] while maintaining constant concentrations of all other reagents. For a ten-fold shift in the initial [Os (VIII)], the graphs between k_o and [Os (VIII)] were linear and nearly extended through the origin, as shown in Fig. 3. Therefore, in an alkaline media, the hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation of chromium (III) alanine catalyzed by Os (VIII) has a reaction order of one with respect to [Os (VIII)]. The results of this study are displayed in Table 3.

Table 3: Effect of [Os (VIII)] on the hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation of Chromium (III) alanine.

$$10^3 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} = 1.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}, 10^2 [\text{CrA}] = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3},$$

$$10^2 [\text{OH}^-] = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ and } \mu = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$$

Temp. (K)	10 ⁵ Os [VIII] (mol dm ⁻³)				
	0.5	1.5	2.5	3.5	5.0
	10 ⁵ k _o (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)				
303	2.92	6.96	11.58	16.13	21.45
308	4.20	9.84	17.24	24.58	31.34
313	5.23	15.54	25.35	31.99	46.57
318	6.12	19.56	32.98	43.64	62.68
323	7.10	22.58	33.98	44.64	66.68

Fig. 3: k_o versus [Os (VIII)] plots for the oxidation of [CrA] at 303K, 308K, 313K, 318K and 323K

Dependence on [Chromium (III) alanine]

The order of the reaction with respect to Chromium (III) alanine was determined by looking at how various [CrA] affected the values of k_o at constant concentrations of all other reagents. In Chromium (III) alanine, the [substrate] was changed ten times.

In every instance, the k_o⁻¹ vs. [CrA]⁻¹ plots were found to be linear, with an intercept on the k_o⁻¹ axis. The data is in Table 4, and these charts are displayed in Fig. 4.

$$10^4 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} = 1.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}, 10^6 \text{ Os [VIII]} = 7.50 \text{ mol dm}^{-3},$$

$$10^2 [\text{OH}^-] = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ and } 10 [\mu] = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}.$$

Temp. (K)	[SUBSTRATE] ⁻¹ (mol ⁻¹ dm ³)				
	1000	500	250	166.66	125
	10 ⁻⁴ k _o ⁻¹ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s)				
303	20.9840	14.2039	9.7585	3.8977	2.7699
308	16.9375	8.9791	5.7802	4.7457	3.3481
313	10.1274	6.3075	3.8969	2.2100	1.7819
318	6.9893	4.8989	3.4974	2.3249	1.3272
323	5.4740	3.7039	2.7565	1.8977	0.7879

Fig 4: k_0^{-1} vs $[\text{CrA}]^{-1}$ plots for the oxidation of Chromium (III) alanine at 303K, 308K, 313K, 318K and 323K.

Effect of the ionic strength:

In order to examine the impact of ionic strength on the Chromium (III) alanine complex, the ionic strength in a typical sodium chloride solution was changed. It was found that the k_0 values rose in every instance as the ionic strength increased.

Where,

X_1 = Product -1
 X_2 = Final Product
 n = No. of molecules of H_2O

It is worth noting that product (1) in the suggested process is created as shown in Eq (5). Under the experimental conditions, product (1) is oxidized in a fast step to Chromic Acid, acetaldehyde, carbon dioxide, and ammonia, which is further supported by stoichiometry and product analysis in the case of Os (VIII) catalysed hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation of Chromium (III) alanine complex.

Conclusion

The hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation of the Chromium (III) alanine complex catalyzed by Os (VIII) has the following essential features:

1. The reaction shows a zero-order correlation with hexacyanoferrate (III).
2. The catalyst-related reaction rate is one since the k_0 vs. $[\text{Os (VIII)}]$ plot is linear and almost reaches the origin.

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3. The pace of the oxidation process rises as $[\text{OH}]^-$ increases.
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